

From the atom to the man: Wycliffe and his fight against the doctrine of transubstantiation.

Author: Leandro Villela de Azevedo

Master and PhD student at USP in Social History

Oriented by professor Nachman Falbel

Summary:

Aspects of the theological conflict between the precursors of the Protestant Reformation and the Catholic Church, center on the issue of transubstantiation. The central point is the analysis of Wycliffe's works, comparing them with Thomistic philosophy.

Key words:

Middle Ages, Medieval Heresies, Catholic Church, John Wycliffe, Transubstantiation

It is difficult to pinpoint the moment in which the doctrine of transubstantiation emerged in the medieval Catholic Church. There are those who argue that Ignatius of Antioch, in 107 AD, defended this thought when he said that “The Eucharist is the flesh

of our Lord”¹. However, the word transubstantiation only began to be used² in the middle of the 11th century, with its theoretical-theological concept well established from Saint Thomas Aquinas, through the *Summa Theologiae*.

Briefly, we can define transubstantiation as the real transformation (material and spiritual) of the bread into the flesh of Christ and the wine into the blood of Christ. Saint Thomas Aquinas dedicates several chapters of his *Summa Theologiae* to defining how this would happen:

1 – The transformation would occur completely and instantly, so that all the bread turns into the body and all the wine turns into blood, thus negating both the idea that the Eucharist was a symbol, and the idea that the body and blood of Christ were only present in the Eucharist. The bread and wine cease to exist once they are transformed into the body and blood of Christ.

2 – This transformation would occur at the moment when the minister, *in persona christi* repeat the words of Jesus at his last supper. The transformation would be instantaneous as soon as the words finished being spoken, if for any reason the minister could not finish the words, due to forgetfulness, death, or other accident, everything would need to be started over.

3 – Once there was transformation, in no way would body and blood return to being bread and wine, therefore, even if administered to other people after the moment of mass, there would be validity as a sacrament.

4 – Only people chosen by the Catholic Church would have the power to minister such transformation, which, according to Saint Thomas Aquinas, cannot be understood by reason, if not by faith.

5 – The body of Christ is present entirely in each part of the transubstantiated bread, and each time it is broken, no matter how many parts it is broken into, each one of them will be the complete body of Christ.

6 – The “body” of Christ into which the bread is transformed is not parts of the body, such as the head, hand, etc., on the contrary, the body is present entirely in each part, including the blood itself, since when If you say body, you refer to the complete body with all its parts, including blood.

¹Letter to the Smyrnese, verse 7

²Hildebert of Tours, 1079

The theological summary dates back to 1272, having reserved 10 questions, subdivided into several articles, to deal with each of its aspects. However, it was only at the Council of Trent, completed in 1562, that the dogma was defended and completely made official. In the meantime, several theologians discussed this doctrine. Among whom we have Wycliffe, one of his main accusers.

John Wycliffe (1320-1383) was a professor of theology at Oxford, having written extensive works in Latin and English. In short, he challenged the papal power, denounced the deviation from the real objectives of the gospel, defended that the Bible was the main authority, and not the tradition of the Church, denounced the errors of the Franciscans, who had lost the ideals of Saint Francis, and, above all, everything, he criticized the doctrine of transubstantiation.

One of his works receives special attention here, *The Wicket*, which had only two printed publications, one in 1546 and another in 1828. This work was aimed at the English people and not the ecclesiastical authorities. The Wicket had such a practical character of raising the people against papal authority that it may even have been the main cause of the peasant uprising of 1381. When Wycliffe uses a term to differentiate Christians from Catholic followers of the pope, the term “Papist”, we have a clear notion of division. Where he does not limit himself to saying that it is possible to be a Christian without being under papal rule, but goes so far as to state that those who accept this rule are not true Christians. They are just letting themselves be led down the broadest path, that of perdition. (The name of the book “Wicket” means narrow path, in reference to the teaching of the “Two Paths” present in the gospels³)

The issue of combating transubstantiation could not be of less importance. We must remember that once the bread and wine are transformed into the very body and blood of Christ, we have the presence of the messiah himself, one of the parts of the Triune God, invoked and physically present among men. More than simply remembering words or reliving a moment, the doctrine of transubstantiation causes Christ to have a real, carnal presence in the life of the believer.

³Where there are two paths, one broad and wide, which leads to perdition and the other narrow and difficult to pass, which leads to salvation. Based on this principle and the persecution suffered by Christ, his apostles and the prophets of Israel, such as Isaiah, Wycliffe argues that true worship of God always occurs in a small group that has true faith, and that is persecuted by a group who commands the official and institutionalized religion, in the time of Christ the Pharisees, in his time, those he calls “papists”

In this way, once the host is consecrated, and therefore transubstantiated, it already acquires its new status, must be protected under lock and key, and was sometimes stolen as it was considered sacred⁴. If the ingestion of this very sacred good, which is the physical and real presence of God himself, can be done by the faithful, then it is the most important and fundamental point of any religious ritual performed, especially masses, where the hosts and the wine is consecrated.

However, believing or not in transubstantiation is not just a religious stance of the believer or the clergy. In fact, when creating a product that is as desired as God himself, which is considered the bread that feeds the soul, having a monopoly on this product that is considered the most sacred that exists, is being able to have control over an entire people.

The control of the Catholic Church does not rest on the production of hosts or wine. A person might be able to acquire some of the wine or bread that would be used in a mass, but they would still be bread and wine. The transubstantiation of the bread into the flesh of Christ and the wine into the blood of Christ would only occur when a priest, through the Eucharist at Mass, made the transformation.

Only priests ordained by the Catholic Church would have the power to transubstantiate bread and wine. Anyone who refused to follow ecclesiastical guidelines could suffer various penalties, but without a doubt the worst of them was excommunication, the act of being prevented from participating in the Eucharist. Thus denying the person access to the product of greatest spiritual value in the Middle Ages.

The ritual itself is simple, the priest, "In Persona Cristis" that is, representing Christ, repeats the words of Jesus at the last supper. At that moment, for an instant, the priest represents Christ himself, therefore God himself, and after the transformation, bread and wine maintain their attributes of Christ's flesh and blood.

Wycliffe goes so far as to explain to us why he should fight transubstantiation so fervently through the following words: "*This superstitious reverence for the elements of the sacrament increases in every possible way the power of the clergy.*"⁵. And "Of all the heresies that have spread through the Church, I believe that none has been brought more maliciously by hypocrites to deceive the people in so many different ways as this;

⁴The 20th Canon of the IV Lateran Council specifically deals with the need to lock the place where the consecrated host and wine were to prevent "their use for impious and blasphemous purposes".

⁵Triialogus, IV, 2

Thus they rob people, make them commit idolatry, deny their faith in the Holy Scripture, and in consequence generate a lack of faith provoking anger in various ways against The Truth.”⁶

The issue of idolatry seems clear. Since the consecrated host is considered God himself, then it would be an image of God, along the lines of the golden statues so repudiated in the Old Testament. However, this argument itself seems merely theological, while the other two are more focused on practical faith.

Wycliffe does not accuse this doctrine of denying Holy Scripture, but rather of denying faith in sacred scripture. Since contact with God can be acquired through a substance, no matter what form it is acquired in, it will bring contact with God. Therefore, there is no need to read the Scriptures or even know the teachings of Jesus and his apostles, just obey the clergy and receive the object of the sacrament.

Opposing Transubstantiation, at first Wicliffe even proposes that the bread and wine were just a symbol and nothing more. As we see in: *“For me, it seems sufficient for Christians to believe that the body of Christ is present in some spiritual and sacramental way in a place that hosts them, to know that God honors the homage paid to His Body and is sensitive to this sacrament, just as He would be sensitive to an image or tomb”*⁷

This conception described by Wicliffe, ultimately, could remove control of official Christianity from the clergy and the Catholic Church. Since the Eucharist is only sacramental, there was no physical transformation. If God honors a tribute performed by man, by eating the bread and drinking the wine by remembering his words, then anyone could perform the sacrament. It would be enough for it to be done in memory of Christ, honoring him, regardless of any established clergy, God would honor such an act. Removing control over the Eucharist from the Catholic Church would be overthrowing one of its centers of power. In the same way that an image or tomb does not have its sacredness because of someone who consecrates it, but it is present in the person buried in the tomb or the image carved in wood, so the Eucharist according to Wicliff would not have its value in whoever consecrates the host, but yes in the symbol present in it, the body of Christ, in memory.

Precisely because he knew the vital importance of the doctrine of transubstantiation, Wicliffe would be attacked from several sides, having to write several

⁶Idem

⁷Early Sermons, No XX – Lambeth - 23

treatises to maintain his thinking. One of the most interesting attacks on transubstantiation is present in *From Ent*, a set of 350 studies, where he refers to “The substance of bread is not annihilated, since its accidents remain”⁸

At this moment Wycliffe is responding to Saint Thomas Aquinas, who in previous centuries defended transubstantiation in several chapters of his *Summa Theologiae*. To better understand Wycliffe's thoughts on this topic and his arguments, it is necessary to first highlight some of the aspects of the defense and justifications raised by Saint Thomas:

A – About the transformation of bread into the flesh of Christ and wine into the blood of Christ.

According to Saint Thomas Aquinas⁹ the transformation is real and not just a symbol. The consecrated bread and wine “contain Christ himself and not just a figurative meaning. His presence is totally true and thus the sacrament contains Christ himself.” This transformation was not simply complete, but it was the basis of faith: “whoever rejects such a statement is considered a heretic as he will be against Christ. Let him abandon his error and accept the true faith.”

In contrast, we have the already cited passage from Wycliffe's *Early Sermons* that says it is sufficient to believe that “in some spiritual and sacramental way” the body is present in the Eucharist. Saint Thomas himself highlights in his document 4 possible objections to the belief that bread and wine actually transform into body and blood:

1 – If Jesus ascended to heaven after his resurrection and preserved a material body, then this material body continues to exist on high, therefore this same body cannot be present in the eucharist.

2 – No one can be in several places at the same time, therefore no one could be present at several altars at the same time, therefore the Eucharist could not be the real body of Christ.

⁸From *Adnichilacione in De Ente*, LVII

⁹*Summa Theologiae*, Third Part, Question 73, article 1

3 – The sacraments are a test of faith, therefore the sacrament of the Eucharist is just the desire for the material presence of Christ, so if Christ were really present materially there would be no need for faith.

4 – When Jesus said that the bread and wine were his body and blood and that they should eat his body and blood, he raised questions, his answer would have implied that the presence of his body and blood would actually be only symbolic and spiritual.

According to Saint Thomas himself, the origin of some of these objections would be Saint Augustine himself. However, as a counterpoint to these arguments he raises only three factors. The first is a quote from Hilarius of Pictavium¹⁰: “There is no doubt about the true presence of the body and blood of Christ, for Our Lord declared and by our faith his flesh is truly eaten and his blood truly drunk.” The second is a quote from Ambrose¹¹: “Just like our Lord Jesus Christ, the true son of God, for it is the true flesh of Christ that we take and the true blood that we drink.”

In these first two factors we only have the citation of important Patristic characters, but who in themselves do not argue in favor of transubstantiation, they only declare it. Unlike the four objections previously raised by Saint Thomas, which outlined rational thought in order to deny such a doctrine.

Thomas Aquinas himself accepts this line of thought when giving his “verdict” on the issue: *The true presence of Christ in the sacrament cannot be perceived nor understood. It's just a matter of faith.* He also does not argue against the objections raised, as he does in other questions, he just makes it clear that Saint Augustine would never have denied transubstantiation, he would have just been misinterpreted by all the heretics who deny such doctrine.

Since transubstantiation is undeniable and inexplicable at the same time, all other questions and articles raised are made only to defend this definite truth *a priori*.

For Wycliffe the figurative point of bread and wine was proved by the fact that Jesus always spoke figuratively. Talking about sheep and coins to talk about sinners, about fishermen of people, about seeds sown as the word of God. In own *Wicketwe* have: When Jesus said “drink from this cup” he was promising everyone who drank that they

¹⁰In his book “De Trinitate”. Hilarius was contemporary with Saint Augustine.

¹¹In his book “De Sacramentis” Also contemporary with Saint Augustine.

would go through tribulations in this world just as he did, but in this way they would also enter eternal life.¹²

B - About why even after consecration the bread continues to look like bread and the wine looks like wine.

Both Wycliffe and Saint Augustine use the term *accident*. These are terms from Aristotelian philosophy. Everything that exists materially can be divided into accident and essence. The latter is what defines something as what it is, for example The human being is a rational being. Or the table is a supported horizontal plane. Learning arithmetic or serving as a support for food is just a consequence of this essence, generating a function for this something. However, everything that is not part of the essence of something is considered an accident. In this way, the man being tall or short, or the table being made of wood or plastic, are just accidents, without in any way influencing their essence.

It is undeniable, both for Saint Thomas and for Wycliffe, that accidents remain even after transubstantiation. In other words, the wine continues to taste like wine, color like wine, smell like wine and looks like wine. The same goes for bread. For Wycliffe, as we have already seen, this consists of two possibilities. Firstly, it denies transubstantiation, since there is no physical or visible transformation that leads us to believe that there really has been any change, or at least that the substance of the bread and wine remains, even if there has been some transformation, it only adds to the essence of the body and blood of Christ to the bread and wine, without annihilating them.

Saint Thomas¹³, however, argues that bread and wine cease to exist, since it would be impossible to see the body of Christ arriving from somewhere and entering the bread, one could only assume that the bread was transformed into the body. Once he has been transformed into the body of Christ, how could he continue to be bread? In this way, bread and wine cease to exist.

¹²The Wicket, p.12

¹³In article 3 of question 75

But, if even though bread and wine are the body and blood of Christ, they continue to have the accidents of bread and wine, that is, they continue to resemble bread and wine in all physical aspects, how could this be explained within transubstantiation?

The answer to this is given in the fifth article of Saint Thomas' text: *It is evident that all the accidents of bread and wine remain after the consecration. And this is reasonably created by Divine Providence. Firstly, it is not customary, if not horrible, for men to eat human flesh and drink blood. (...) Secondly, because this way the sacrament cannot be given to those who do not believe and thirdly, because by receiving the body and blood of Christ invisibly we gain merit for our faith.*

Saint Thomas does not make it clear why the fact that the accidents of bread and wine persist would prevent the sacrament from being given to those who do not believe, since the body and blood of Christ are really present there, and are not there just as a symbol of faith.

C – About the moment or period in which the bread and wine are transformed into the body and blood of Christ.

As simple as the ritual of consecrating the bread and wine is, it is not instantaneous. More than that, repeating Jesus' words, we have the ritual in two stages. First he took the bread, gave thanks and gave it to his disciples, saying that it was his body. In the same way, at the end of supper, he took the chalice, gave thanks and handed it to everyone, telling them to take it and drink because it was his blood.

According to Wycliffe, these two steps would be a clear reason why transubstantiation could not occur. Let's see: *"But now I will ask you a question and you will answer me. Was Our Lord's body made once or twice? Are the body and blood of Christ present only in the bread? Or was the body made once and the blood made at another time? It is also said that the wine was in the cup. If you say that it was full and the whole body of Christ was present in the bread, including the flesh and blood, and also here the bones, then you are making us worship a false God in the cup. Which is also answered when we are worshiping the bread if we say that the flesh is in the bread and the blood in the wine, then you will be believing that Christ's humanity is divided and He is made in twofold, for he first takes the bread and then share the bread, as it is said.*

*And innocent people are idolizing this bread. But I am also certain that the body and blood of Christ ascended. Then he would be a false charlatan for God and for us.*¹⁴

Despite being a small section, Wycliffe poses several obstacles to transubstantiation. Firstly, the fact that the transformation occurs in two different parts. Later the issue of blood and body being separated from each other.

Saint Thomas was also concerned with the same issue, going so far as to state that *The* transformation takes place instantly¹⁵ because God's power is immense and can bring about instantaneous transformations. The example he gave is that a finite source of heat cannot evaporate all the water at once, but as God has infinite power he can carry out transformations instantly.

But if the transformation occurs once and instantaneously, then when does it occur? When is the bread consecrated or when the wine is consecrated? Saint Thomas answers this in his question 83, the transformation occurs at the moment when the priest has finished proclaiming the last words, that is, only after consecrating the bread and wine. He even worries about several possible problems related to this, for example, what to do if the priest dies in the middle of saying the words, having started to say them but not finished. The answer would be given in two ways, firstly that people who are sick or close to death should not in any way participate in this consecration, but even if something were to happen, any other priest could take the place of the deceased and continue to speak the words from where he had been. just said. Or even, what should be done if the priest, due to shivering from the cold or old age, dropped a few drops of wine on the floor while speaking the words of consecration? The answer would be to stop everything immediately and start again from the beginning, as transubstantiation would occur in all the wine and not just in what remained in the chalice. Finally, what should you do if a priest stutters, makes a mistake, repeats a word or omits a word during the consecration? He must start everything over again, but St. Thomas says that people who really pay attention will not let this happen.¹⁶

Now, precisely because of this excessive zeal in a mystical, almost magical ritual, so that the bread and wine actually transformed into the body and blood of Christ, Wycliffe accused those who believed of idolatrous transubstantiation. The rules, the words, the ritual, seemed more important than the meaning behind it. *"This is your worst*

¹⁴The Wicket, p.09

¹⁵Question 75, Article 7

¹⁶Question 83, article 6

mistake, that of non-belief. Before you is the worst of sins, for it is written that when Moses was on the mountain with God, people made a golden calf and worshiped it as if it were a God. And God spoke to Moses that people had committed the worst of sins, made and worshiped foreign gods."¹⁷

C – Bread is only flesh and wine is only blood, or both together are body and blood at the same time?

As we have already seen in Wycliffe's exposition, there are certain implications if we take Jesus' statement that the wine is his blood and the bread is his flesh literally. If the consecrated bread is only the body of Christ, then it should in no way be considered Christ himself, since a person is not made only of his body. And if wine is only blood, it could not be considered Christ himself. Furthermore, wouldn't blood be a part of the body? If that were the case, then it would be enough for the bread to be consecrated, since it would already contain blood and body. Furthermore, there is the question, if bread is meat and wine is blood, where would the bones, eyes, hair, etc. be?

Once again, Saint Thomas already had an answer to this question. *"Each species of the sacrament certainly contains the whole of Christ (...) this is because the body of Christ had not been separated from his blood until the moment of his passion and death."*¹⁸ . In this way, part of Wycliffe's questions are resolved, but not all. If both bread and wine are truly sufficient in themselves, why is there a need for both? And why would Jesus have spoken separately of his flesh and blood? There is, in sum Theology, no question about that. Obviously we must keep in mind that Saint Thomas wrote almost two centuries before Wycliffe, therefore not responding to him, but to contemporary questions about him.

But strangely, Wycliffe does not use the *Summa Theologiae* to raise his arguments, even raising arguments that would have already been debunked 200 years before they were made by him. What is the reason for this? Perhaps simply because he denies the generating principle of all statements, as we have already seen, faith without

¹⁷The Wicket, p.9

¹⁸Question 76, article 2

justification, or perhaps because he is writing directly to the people and not in theological treatises. Still, why not mention Saint Thomas Aquinas?

D – Physics and faith – How to explain transubstantiation while maintaining the rules of the physical world?

Wycliffe places several flaws in transubstantiation by simply understanding the physical world and the physical impossibility of the real and material transformation of bread and wine into the body and blood of Christ. In *Wicket* itself we have the following quote:

If the body and blood are not simply present in the bread and wine, but are the wine and bread themselves transformed, then this opens the door to a number of possibilities. Firstly, if bread is only a part of the body of Christ, then why should anyone receive only a part of the bread, it would be right to eat as much of the consecrated bread as possible. At the same time, if the body and blood are present in their entirety in each loaf, then how can the same body be present in several places at the same time? And if the body is present in its entirety in one of the loaves, if that loaf is cut in half, will each part still have the entire body? How is it possible for Jesus to continue to have his body if his body is now transformed bread? These are some of the questions raised by Wycliffe.

Some of these have already been answered by Saint Thomas Aquinas in his *Summa Theologiae*. "It is evident that the whole nature of the substance is in every part of the dimensions which contain it, just as the whole nature of the air is contained in every part of the air, and the whole nature of the bread is in every part of the bread, and this occurs in a way that is indifferent to its dimensions and independent of the number of times it is cut or divided (...) So each part manifests the entire Christ in each part of the two species"¹⁹

This definition given by Thomas Aquinas seems to resolve, in part, Wycliffe's statements. In this way Jesus is seen almost as a chemical element, the definition given

¹⁹Question 76, Article 3

by him is very similar to the idea of an atom, both in ancient Greek philosophy and, in a certain way, in modern chemistry. Almost as if Christ were one of the elements on the periodic table. Therefore, the essence of Christ would be present in every part of the bread and wine, completely, and it would not matter how much bread or wine was there.

The philosophical argument reaches such a point that it seems to completely forget that it is an initially human body, like that of any other person, which was actually born from a woman, slept, ate and went through any deprivations and needs of any human being. When being substantiated and atomized, it does not matter who Jesus really was, what his teachings and examples were, what matters is that this substance is produced through consecration in the Eucharist and consumed by the faithful.

Saint Thomas continues his text as follows: “the example of an image that only appears in a mirror. It only appears as long as the mirror is not broken, but when the mirror is broken there is a complete image in each part of the broken mirror. In this way the comparison is not perfect, because the multiplication of these images is the result of a broken mirror and made because of the various reflections in the various parts of the mirror, but there is only one in the consecration, the Body of Christ is in this sacrament.”²⁰

The mirror is used by Saint Thomas to demonstrate the sacrament as only symbolic, since the image in the mirror is just an image and not the person present in the glass. He uses this example to show how this comparison would be invalid or imperfect, proving, once again, that the sacrament could not really be symbolic, but a transformation in fact.

Wycliffe, in turn, responds to Thomas Aquinas' argument in his book *Wicket*: “Just as a man can hold up a mirror and observe the great resemblance to his own face and yet it is not his face, it is only the image of your face. To say that it really is his face, the man would need to have two faces, one on his body and the other in the mirror. And if the mirror were to break into several parts, it would have several faces, more through the glass than through the body. And so each man could create for himself as many faces as he wanted. Then he can see the likeness of his face, an image of her and not the face itself. So the bread is a figure of the body of Christ on Earth, and this is what Christ said: Whenever you do these things, do them in memory of me.”²¹

²⁰Idem

²¹The Wicket, p.12

At first, the argumentation used by Wycliffe may seem strange, since he uses precisely the argumentation considered by Saint Thomas as imperfect and as a symbol of denial. However, analyzing more carefully we can see that he does use arguments contrary to the thought present in the *Summa Theologiae*.

He places the figure of a man holding the mirror. And even before the mirror breaks, he already demonstrates that it would be impossible for man to hold the mirror and at the same time be present inside the mirror. Although it may seem like an unfounded argument that does not match the thoughts of Saint Thomas, here we have the return of the figure of Christ as a man and not as a mere chemical element.

Elem also places the figure of this man coexisting with his image, that is, Jesus still existing and having his body at the same time that the eucharist is made. After all, it would be impossible to deny that Jesus existed at that time without shaking the structures of medieval faith.

Now, the image used by Thomas Aquinas is completely opposite to that used by Wycliffe, he uses air, something ethereal, incorporeal, invisible, distant from humanity. It would be impossible for air to hold a mirror, or bread. Even if there were a loaf capable of holding the bread itself, either all of it would be broken and divided among the people, and therefore there would be no more man-bread left, or else everyone would see that only a part was ingested by the people, since the man-bread would remain.

But that's not the only issue. Wycliffe gives Jesus his face back. In his example only the face is reflected in the mirror. A body is made up of several parts, face with eyes, mouth, nose and hair; trunk with limbs, limbs with endings, feet and hands, each with its fingers, each with its nails. It is not just an ethereal substance capable of mixing and fusing, it is not the amorphous substance of bread dough that can be portioned and maintain each of its characteristics even in the smallest of parts of the unbaked bread.

Wycliffe even tells us of the mirror breaking into several small parts. In fact, the image of the mirror breaking had already been used by Saint Thomas, this in itself would be enough justification for Wycliffe to use the same image. However, from the other factors already compared, we see that Wycliffe does not have much concern in responding to Saint Thomas' arguments, on the contrary, he seems more interested in creating his own thought and transmitting it to a people who probably suffered the consequences of Saint Thomas' justifications. Thomas, but without knowing this thought in his more philosophical-academic arguments.

Why then does he resort to the same image of the mirror breaking? Because at the time of the Eucharist the bread is divided into several parts and each person has only one of these parts. If we go deeper, the division is even greater, since the Eucharist takes place in thousands of churches, monasteries and cathedrals spread across Europe. The image used by Wycliffe is that when the mirror is broken, it produces a greater number of faces than the body itself had, which was just one. Thus, if each of these faces were real, there would be more faces present in the mirror fragments than actually in the body that previously held that mirror. That is, if transubstantiation really occurs, then there would be more Christ in the bread and wine than in Christ himself.

But in doing so, Wycliffe also makes clear the image that those “Christs” that could be present in each of the fragments could never be the same “Christ” present from the outside, as the figure of the man who initially held the mirror. And although Wycliffe did not make the following statement clear, it would be logical to use such a metaphorical comparison. As soon as the man moved away from the fragmented mirror, he would return to being just a mirror, reflecting anything that came close to him, and there would be no point in keeping a piece of broken glass if he simply denied the figure of someone who had your own image reflected in this glass.

The way Wycliffe ends his comparison is even more interesting: “and thus said Christ: Whenever you do these things, do them in memory of me” If until then, although he used the same figure, he might not have been responding to Saint Thomas , in this biblical quote he seems to be responding directly to the only scriptural argument used in the Summa to prove that transubstantiation really occurred: “This is my body that will be given up for you” Cyril says: We cannot doubt that this is true but we must take these words of faith from our Savior, for he is true. He doesn’t lie”²²

When quoting “Every time you do these things, do them in my memory” Wycliffe uses other words of Jesus that prove that everything should be done in memory, as a symbol, to remember, and not as a real transformation. If Jesus is true and does not lie, then the same principle would be valid for this other sentence, so that all of this would then be just a memorial action.

²²Question 75, article 1

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